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Nigeria-China Relations and Trade Development in Nigeria, 2015-2022

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ABSTRACT

Nigeria socio-economic development relations with China has been in place, since 1971, over a decade after Nigeria gained independence from the British realm. These relations have expanded both growing into money lending, bilateral trade and socio-economic development strategic cooperation. It is within this basis that the general purpose of this study was to investigate the Nigeria-China relations and trade development in Nigeria, basically focused on trade relations and its impacts on the socio-economic development in Nigeria, 2015-2022. Specifically the study examined how Nigeria-China relations shaped trade in Nigeria and evaluated how Nigeria-China relations impacted on the socio-economic development in Nigeria. The study adopted dependency, complex inter-dependency, imperialism, neo-colonialism and globalization theories as the theoretical framework. The study used qualitative research design method. Documentary method for data collection was used which include; published and unpublished documents and official government gazettes, textbooks, journals, articles, newspaper and internet. The data generated for this study was analyzed using textual method of data analysis. The findings of this study revealed that China's economic goals are driven by strong political, ideological, and economic ambitions rather than selflessness. The finding of this study also stated that Nigeria-China trade development relations is of imbalance trade between the two nation states; the term of trade between the two countries shows that Nigeria's import is greater than her export hence; China has gained more than Nigeria in the long run especially in the area of oil exploration and exploitation. And it further indicated that the impacts of Nigeria relations with China have helped to secure access to financing aimed at revamping Nigeria's agricultural sector, building projects, infrastructures, security equipment, education, socio-economic development and overall food production. The study concluded that there is an un equal relationship between Nigerian and China, resulting to trade imbalance and dependency on Nigeria side. China relations with Nigeria have revamped and financed Nigeria Agricultural sector, transportation and bilateral trade and food production. Amongst the recommendations is that the researcher recommended that Nigeria should improve the effectiveness of its local technician training and attempt to retain them. This will determine the project's success and lay the groundwork for Nigeria's future industrialization and all loans from China should be properly channeled to projects that improve the welfare of citizens; efforts should be made to ensure accountability in the use of all loans received so that future generations are not harmed. The Nigerians' mentality that China's current trade relation is a favourable one needs to be changed. Rather, Nigeria must seek to accept only trade partnerships that would benefit the country rather than the one that will continue to limit the country. Issues of political instability, insecurity, dilapidated infrastructure, capacity building through functional education and economic diversification among others must be addressed by Nigeria against over dependence on the West and China for socio-economic development in Nigeria and that Nigerian Government should depend less on the import of goods from China since it affects economic growth in terms of real domestic product. They should start to produce their goods and consume them.

Keywords: Nigeria-China, Relations, Trade Development, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria established diplomatic relation with the Peoples' Republic of China (PRC) in 1971. The relationships were mostly passive until the general Sani Abacha regime that had global rejection of its policies and many sanction imposed on Nigeria. The isolation of the regime made Nigeria in 1999 to cultivate new friends in the global community. Among the countries Nigeria cultivated relationship with was China, following the founding in 1994 of the Nigeria Chinese Chamber of Commerce

(Idigo, 2025). In 1997, the Nigerian delegation led by Abdulsalam Abubakar was sent by General Abacha to China. After the death of General Abacha, Abdulsalam further consolidated the relationship. President Obasanjo embarked on several diplomatic initiatives which included official visits to China in 2003 and 2007 to meaningfully engage Chinese companies.

Development is a process that creates growth, progress, positive change or the addition of physical, economic, environmental, social and demographic components. The purpose of development is a rise in the level and quality of life of the population, and the creation or expansion of local regional income and employment opportunities, without damaging the resources of the environment (Idigo, 2024). At the level of the individual it implies increase skill and capacity, greater freedom, creativity, self-discipline, responsibility and material wellbeing.

Socio-economic development is a product of development and can be defined as the process of social and economic transformation in a society. Socio-economic development embraces changes taking place in the social sphere mostly of an economic nature. Thus, socio-economic development is made up of processes caused by exogenous and endogenous factors which determine the course and direction of the development and development cannot be achieved in any nation where there are conflicts, crisis and war (Chandler, 2017; Stan 2014).

China-Nigeria socio-economic development relations have been heavily criticized in the press and in academic writings. Sanusi, former governor of the Central Bank of Nigeria, stated in 2013 that "China takes primary goods from us and sells them to us as manufactured goods (Sanusi, 2013)." This was the essence of colonialism as well. Others have also been harsh. According to Agubamah (2014), the Nigeria-China trade development relations is a lose-lose situation, not a win-win situation, as China claims. He continued by stating that Nigeria should not be used as a dumping ground for low-cost Chinese imports. The Chinese government, on the other hand, sees its investment in Africa especially in Nigeria as a "win-win" situation that benefits both China and Africa. At the 2018 Forum on China-Africa Cooperation (FOCAC), China's President Xi Jinping argued that the goal of China-Africa socio-economic development relations is to make "lives better for our people," and that cooperation should benefit both China and Africa (Tiezzi, 2018). The relationship between Chinese investment and economic growth, on the other hand, is a hotly debated topic, and specific areas of engagement, such as natural resource-backed loans, have been heavily criticized (Strange, 2013; Alves, 2013).

The reciprocal economic relation between China and Nigerian has been linked to their similarities in ethnic diversities, as well as in their rich endowments in demographics, minerals and human resources (Udeala, 2013). Although unlike Nigeria, China, to a large extent, has been able to harness her vast demographic, human and material resources to build a strong and profitable domestic economy that has impacted on the economic development of the rest of the world in recent times (Gubak & Maiwada, 2015).

From the foregoing, it can be argued that "with China's self-elevation into the club of the industrialized economic powers, Nigeria has, to a large extent, surpassed the initial status entrusted upon her by the European imperialists as a dependent nation on the economies of the West. Notably, the economy of China is gradually overwhelming those of Europe, United States, Canada and Japan in recent time (Aaron, 2019). The country's proven expertise in iron ore, steel, aluminum, textile, electronics, agriculture, petroleum, and transportation industries, as well as her exports of these materials to Europe, USA, Canada, Japan, and to the rest of the world, shows that China has overtaken the nations of Western Europe and the United States and Canada in the sales of export commodities in the international market (Akwen, 2011). It is against this backdrop that this study sought to critically examine the Nigeria-China relations and trade development in Nigeria, 2015-2022 with a view to establishing the facts on the implications and challenges of the relations.

Statement of the Problem

Nigeria-China Relations are characterized by trade imbalance. A trade imbalance refers to a situation where a country imports significantly more goods and services than it exports resulting in a negative balance of trade or a trade deficit.

It is an unequal exchange of goods between nations. The World Bank (2019) reported that China recorded a USD.3.3 billion trade surplus against Nigeria in 2017 <https://zypd.com.ng>. In 2022, Chinese exports to Nigeria amounted to \$15.67 billion, but Nigeria export to China accounted for a mere \$1.58 billion. <https://assets.kpmg.com>.

Nigeria's relations on trade development with China have developed into one of the major bilateral relations of any country since diplomatic relations were established on 10 February 1971. In addition to high-level visits, Chinese companies and money found their way into Nigeria, the largest economy in Africa (The Conversation, 2021). It is imperative to note that the relationship between Nigeria and China is not without any challenges. Notwithstanding, several analysts have called for a re-examination of the relations between Nigeria and China, especially as China is seen as a scrambler, invader, and colonizer of the 21st century. This is because China's concern is only with the export of its finished products with less value added to the Nigerian primary products, which are exported as raw materials into China. China, railways, hydrocarbons, telecommunications, agriculture and roads have invaded almost all Nigerian economic sectors in 2016 (Adigbuo, 2019). The floods of the market with cheap Chinese products have led to untold consequences for the weak industrial sector of Nigeria by local manufacturing companies. As Nigeria strives to produce low-tech products, such as textiles and detergents, Chinese products are in stifling competition (The Conversation, 2021).

One of the current challenges in China-Nigeria socio-economic development relations is the negative impact of China's imports on Nigerian industries, in which the biggest casualty has been textiles. For example, an estimated 28,000 Nigerians lost their jobs to Chinese imports in Kano state alone, which is considered to be one of the main textile cities in northern Nigeria in 2015 (The Conversation, 2021). Furthermore, Chinese engage in illegal textiles trade in Kano which Nigerian law forbids. In Nigeria, Chinese trade in textiles with Africa is an emotive problem. Many Nigerians have been blamed for Chinese cheap imports in recent decades for the decline in local textile mills (The Conversation, 2021). Chinese firms have been known to stifle local products by pushing non-standard goods to Nigeria. But part of China's strategy, an economic measure that Nigerian government invented, is a complete rejection of import substitution. Indeed, the inconsistent perception of import substitution between the two States is a worrying challenge (Adigbuo, 2019). Under this condition, Nigeria may explore the most appealing features of Chinese companies and encourage them to develop their manufacturing equipment in the country. The pursuit of industrialization in Nigeria leads to the concept of technology transfer. Technology transfer is the process by which science findings from scientific research are tailored to solve social needs, which is highly practiced by the less advanced nations like Nigeria. China is not a Santa Claus and is persuaded that its bases for relevance in the international system should be protected. China is only willing to launch Nigeria's orbit satellite after some payments have been made. Before then the Chinese scientists and the Asian monarch are not ready to disclose the modalities to Nigeria (Adigbuo, 2019; The Conversation, 2021). Another current to note is trade protectionalism. Before opening its borders to foreigners, China took the road of isolation, like the United States. There is a need for trade protection if Nigeria needs to develop and its slender industry beginnings (Adigbuo, 2019; The Africa Report, 2020). The Nigerian market is flooded by an unprotected market with any kind of Chinese products including toothpicks, exercise books, domestic bulbs, textiles and cutleries. Unprotected trade has huge consequences (The Africa Report, 2020). Many Nigerians are unemployed, and social crimes about which China is worried are caused by unemployment. Although some argue that Chinese companies now operate in Nigeria, there were thousands of Chinese visitors in Nigeria who were not able to work in Nigeria. These Chinese visitors are protected by Chinese companies and are employed in Nigeria (Adigbuo, 2019). While Nigerians languish in prisons in China because of violations of basic immigration laws; every Chinese is an expatriate in Nigeria who sometimes needs to be protected by the Nigerian Immigration Service (Adigbuo,)

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

China-Nigeria Economic Relations

According to Utomi (2017), economic relations between the two countries have grown in the last decade from limited and intermittent contact to an increasingly complex business engagement. However, Nigeria is experiencing economic deficit with China due to higher imports of Chinese goods in relative to exports from Nigeria to China. The present reality is suggesting that this trade deficit may grow except if Nigeria can increase its home-grown options with better quality and competitive prices (Utomi, 2017). In a data from UNCTAD (2018), movement of goods from Africa to China has been in extractive resources between 2012 and 2017. Singularly, fuels and Oil

constituted 62% and 60% of the total exports to China between 2002 and 2013 (Pigato and Tang, 2015). Other products are natural and unrefined, which constitutes 32% accounting for 92% of exports to China. This is against over 94.6 % imports from China which were in manufactured goods, amounting to trade deficit of almost \$19.5 billion annually from 2012 to 2017 (UNCTAD, 2018).

However, several authors had queried the focus of China relationship with Africa and by extension Nigeria. According to Alden (2005), the main focus of Chinese relationship with Nigeria is to access the untapped raw materials domiciled in Africa and Nigeria specifically. This, according to Alden (2005) was observed in China's predominant focus on energy, new market and investment opportunity, under the umbrella of cooperation and mutual support on major issues (Konings (2007). Zweig and Jianhai (2005) opines that China - Nigeria policy is driven by robust China development strategy which brought out need for access to energy resources and export opportunities for its manufacturing, agro-processing, textile, and communications potentials. According to Chen, (2016), there are 221 and 297 Chinese Companies in Nigeria with over 141 listed with Chinese Ministry of Commerce (MOFCOM) been operating in Nigeria while 92 were registered with Nigerian Investment Promotion Council (NIPC), out of which almost 30 of these companies were only into manufacturing activities (Idigo, 2022)

Several factors have characterized the Nigeria - China relationship, with the aid factor, migration programme and the Chinese investment and infrastructure loans made China's relationship with Nigeria unique. Accordingly Sautman & Hairong (2007) and Ramos (2004) aver that the attitude of China government towards local politics, and non-interference policy and focus on infrastructural investment is a major factor. Wenping, (2007) opines that the factor of China values attached to the sovereignty, international relations, consensus building and problem solving is a major issue. Sautman and Hairong, (2007) argues that China approach to economic issues with Nigeria is in contrast with Washington neo-liberal approach of democracy, good governance, and poverty reduction. Zafar, (2007) agrees that the Chinese model of investment is capable of assisting economic growth and development in Africa as it usually has "no strings attached" to all investment and infrastructure loans. Brautigam, (2003) reiterated that most loans advanced by China are at near-zero percent interest, long term facilities. According to Taylor, (2006) this could be responsible for the Chinese investment moving above US\$100 billion mark since decade.

The Taylor's argument has also spurred scholars to research into Nigeria-China Trade Relations and its impact on Nigeria socio-economic development (Alden, 2005; De Lorenzo, 2007). For instance, Alden (2005) stated that most of the Chinese sponsored projects in Nigeria and Sub-Saharan Africa has been complained to be using Chinese labour rather than local workers. This is buttressed by the assertion of the Economist, (2018) which gave an estimate of 264,000 Chinese workers in Africa, a data that show an increase from 181,000 in 2011. The figures excluded informal migrants that are estimated to be more than a million (Economist, 2018). Not only this, the impact of Chinese markets on African enterprises and exports has been described as 'bothersome' (De Lorenzo, 2007). This is evident in Nigeria textiles industries where the produce from China has led to the closure of local factories (De Lorenzo, 2007).

Furthermore, Anshan (2007) has argued that China relations are having serious unemployment effects on Nigeria. He informed that conflict over unethical labour practices employed by some Chinese companies is causing conflict with local labour laws and cultures in Nigeria. Due to closing of major companies as a result of inability to compete with Chinese companies flooding of the markets in Nigeria, many employees are losing their jobs. Thus, Chinese companies are not contributing to the increase in local employment rate and local economy. Also, conflict also exist in the quality of Chinese goods which is perceived to be varied, based on the importers specification but could be of better quality than locally produced ones with a higher price (Anshan, 2007). Also, Nigeria-China Trade relation has been argued to raise a moral issue. For instance, Zweig and Jianhai (2005) argued that Chinese companies are reputable for violent relationship with host nations as experienced in Sudan, Nigeria, Ethiopia, and Zambia. For instance, in Zambia's copper belt of Chambishi protesting employees were sprayed with gunfire by Chinese supervisors (Trofimov, 2007).

There are other scholars who maintain a middle opinion on Nigeria-China trade relationship. Scholars such as Agbebi and Virtanen, (2017); Mlambo, (2016) sees the relationship as more 'opportunity' than a threat to Africa. The scholars advocated for exploring the opportunities that exist in the relationship especially as a response to trade deficit in manufacturing goods from our abundant

natural resources. The scholars argued that one of the best ways is to elicit the interest of Chinese companies to come and produce in Nigeria, utilizing the Economic Processing Zones (EPZ) (Stein, 2012). These, scholars believe that Nigeria-China relation would boost Nigeria to the path of industrialization. This argument has been countered by Harry (2016, 2018) in his research when he found out that in almost twelve (12) EPZ created by Nigeria Export Processing Zone Authority (NEPZA) they had contributed only 4% to non-oil export in Nigeria. Also, in terms of inputs from local raw materials, only 29% were sourced with only 46% of managers being nationals of Nigeria.

Nigeria-China Trade Relations

Generally, scholars agree that trade relations between Nigeria and China have blossomed, although with cautionary caveat. The relations, no doubt, are multidimensional with Chinese proxy-presence evident in many African states especially Nigeria and in all sectors of their economy. Thus, one can rightly agree with that China's trade relations with Nigeria have evolved from the ideologically-driven solidarity of anti-colonialism and the Cold war to pragmatic market-oriented economic engagement. Ideally, economic aid remains central to the entire fulcrum of Chinese-Nigeria foreign policy. This entails aid becoming the principal instrument for permeating the African socio-economic and political membrane (Onuoha et al., 2008). More so quoting avers comes to reckoning that most Africa states especially Nigeria developed their trade relations with China in the context of the aid war between China, the Soviet Union and the United States Peace Corps wherein China has offered aid to its African partners ranging from building infrastructure to treating infectious diseases such as malaria and HIV/AIDS, with the annual volume of trade between China and Africa put at \$5.6 billion in 1999, which quintupled after the establishment of the CACT, making the Sino-African trade to hit \$29.5 billion in 2004 and further growing to \$32.2 billion towards the end of 2005 (Thompson, et al., 2005, Guixuan, et al., 2005, Nwanolue, Iwuoha, et al., 2012). In particular, he revealed that Nigeria trade with China has been growing at an average of more than 50 percent annually since 2002. In the whole, China has taken determined steps to promote trade and economic exchanges between it and Africa. According to China has established centers for investment, trade and development in 11 African countries since 1995 while the Chinese State Council in 1997 established a team to coordinate China's economic, trade and technological cooperation with Africa to the point that the Bank of China has set up its first agency for business operations in Africa (Onuoha et al., 2008)

It is instructive, nonetheless, to point out the fact that China's relations with Africa received a boost in 1950s and 1960s when international relations scholars believe that African continent suddenly became what is globally acclaimed to be the focus of dual maneuvers. However, argued that China's selfless aid to African countries was what laid a solid foundation for the development of bilateral economic relations Onuoha et al., 2008. It is believed in diplomatic circles that the increasing tempo of China's activities is meant to consolidate her hold on Nigeria as Africa's most important trading partner south of the Sahara. Thus, since May 1999 after Nigeria returned to constitutional democracy, President Olusegun Obasanjo visited China twice in 2001 and 2005 with his Chinese counterpart reciprocating both visits. Many high-level visits also took place between ministries and top officials of both countries, yielding lots of benefits to both nations including agreements on trade, investment promotion and protection, supporting agreements on sincere friendship, mutual trust, mutual economic benefit and common development and enhanced consultation and mutual support signed during President Obasanjo's 2001 visit; the agreement for the avoidance of double taxation and the prevention of fiscal evasion with taxes on income signed in April 2002; agreement on consular affairs, cooperation on strengthening management of narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances and diversion of precursor chemical and the agreement on tourism cooperation in July 2002; strategic partnership agreement on mutual political trust, mutual economic benefit and mutual support in international affairs in 2005; an agreement for the construction of water schemes for 19 states and the Federal Capital Territory at the cost of N 695 million on 13th October 2005; and four agreements and three Memoranda of Understanding on a range of programmes to enhance their economic ties during President Hu Jintao's visit to Nigeria in April 2006 (Nwachukwuet al., 2015).

Generally speaking, the general principles and objectives of China's Nigerian policy are as follows:

Sincerity, Friendship and Equality: China adheres to the five principles of peaceful coexistence (sincerity, friendship, equality, mutual benefit and common development), respects Nigeria's independent choice of the road of development and supports Nigeria's efforts to grow stronger through unity.

Mutual Benefit, Reciprocity and Common Prosperity: China supports Nigeria's endeavor for economic development and nation-building, carries out cooperation in various forms in the economic and social development, and promotes common prosperity of China and Nigeria.

Mutual Support and Close Coordination: China will strengthen cooperation with Nigeria in the United Nations and other multilateral systems by supporting each other's just demand and reasonable propositions and continue to appeal to the international community to give more attention to questions concerning peace and development in Nigeria.

Learning from Each Other and seeking Common Development: China and Nigeria will learn from and draw upon each other's experience and cooperation in education, science, culture and health. Supporting Nigeria's efforts to enhance capacity building, China will work together with Nigeria in the exploration of the road of sustainable development (Ezirim G, et al., 2007).

Specifically, China identified four major areas of cooperation with Nigeria as follows:

- a. To promote trade, investment, economic and technical cooperation while enhancing the scale and level of cooperation
- b. To strengthen communication and collaboration in information technology and electronic commerce
- c. To intensify dialogue and consultation mechanism between Chinese and African governments so as to address problems occurring during cooperation, enhance communication, draw upon each other's experiences and make common progress
- d. To consolidate our coordination and cooperation in international and regional economic organizations and endeavor to achieve economic prosperity development of China and Africa, and safeguarding the interest of developing countries (Onuoha, et al., 2008). Equally, in pursuit of the realization of these goals and promote trade and investment relations with Nigeria, China has adopted various strategies which include: Taking positive measures to facilitate African products to enter China market and to give zero tariff treatment to part of exports from least developing countries in Africa, to enlarge the trade scale and optimize the trading structure. China has signed free trade agreement or regional trade assignment with African countries and regional organizations.

African is one of the regions China government encourages enterprises to make investment. Chinese government will formulate and perfect related policy, simplify investment procedures, enhance guide and service, and support powerful enterprises to invest in Africa. She will continue to sign and carry out bilateral agreement to encourage and guarantee investment, and avoiding double taxation to safeguard the legal rights of investors; encouraging China's financial institutions to set up branches in Africa, to provide effective financial service for China-Africa trade and strengthening information service system to create conditions to exploit African market (Onuoha et al., 2008).

However, despite the belief that the relations have some mutual benefits and are more responsive towards the needs of Africa and Nigeria especially when compared with their western counterparts, the reality remains that the relations are yet to be stepped up to the level that both the continent and Nigeria can compete with the rest of the continent in the world market. In fact, it is this lacuna that is responsible for the worry and suspicion associated with the trade relations between the metropolis China and peripheral African countries, including Nigeria. As puts it, China's involvement in Africa via financial aid, foreign direct investment, trade policy and trade flows instigate controversial debate within academic literature. And the question that follows is whether China's economic involvement actually fosters development in Africa cum Nigeria or is simply another form of exploitation of Africa's natural resources so as to sustain China's growth.

Chinese Loans and Nigeria's Socio-Economic Development

Generally speaking, Nigeria's external borrowings especially from China have both negative and positive impacts. Scholars like and believe that the benefits of the relationship between Nigeria and China have become most evident and that African countries have generally found their development partnership with China more concretely beneficial and more satisfying than their experience with the Western donor countries. Oloyede (2002) specifically elaborated on this by revealing that African countries are much more comfortable with Chinese lending's since China's approach to its aid and trade relationship with Africa attaches no strings in the face of the issues such as human rights, and are viewed as offering far more practical and concrete kinds of support such as infrastructure development that is essential for Africa's development but has been neglected by traditional donors.

He revealed that China funds or undertakes projects decided by African countries rather than dictating priorities, apart from the fact that China is quicker to deliver on aid promises than Western countries. However, there is no gainsaying the fact and as pointed out that there are complex and multifaceted dynamics and challenges in the Sino-Nigeria bilateral relations. It is certainly no overkill to state categorically and sadly too that as democracy gets older in African societies like Nigeria with more external borrowings, socio-economic and political problems are yet to take their exit through solutions to poverty, unemployment and more importantly debt crisis. Put differently, the economy of Africa has failed to demonstrate capacity for self-reliance and poverty alleviation despite the economic relations. For Nigeria, the level of domestic savings is not yet sufficient to ensure that development takes place (Ogbeifun, 2007). The consequential effect is that the need to borrow externally in order to bridge the gap between the level of savings and investment is defeated, thereby leading to the conclusion that Chinese loans together with other foreign aids have failed to actualize economic development for Nigeria and as well as pull her large population out of extreme poverty (Ajayi & Oke, et al., 2012, Omoruyi S, et al., 2005, World Bank, 2019).

Perhaps, a more scientific way to determine the effect of external borrowings cum China loans on Nigeria is to interrogate the statistics released by which emphatically stated that 82.9 million Nigerians or 40.1% of the population are considered poor by national standards (Pattillo, 2002). That rate of poverty in Nigeria remains on an increasing trajectory is indeed an antithesis to the foreign assistance received over the years. More so, since 2015, economic growth remains muted, growth averaged 1.9% in 2018 and remained stable at 2% in the first half of 2019 with growth too low to lift bottom half of the population out of poverty (Aluko & Arowolo, 2010). This pathetic condition makes a mess of the projection by as well as which hold that borrowings should create multiplier effect and positively jump-start and accelerate improved productivity via gross domestic product, bigger export market, enhanced exchange rate and overall economic reliance (Mbanga & International Monetary Fund, 2000). By implication, borrowings should salvage the sad situation and give life to the economy.

However, this is not so in Nigeria and the fact remains as, observes, that the present administration in Nigeria had borrowed to offset accumulated salaries and pensions of workers in the states. Urama (2018) in other words, Nigeria had borrowed for consumption and so far failed to juxtapose borrowings with meaningful investments in productive sectors for the sake of achieving economic development. The resultant effect is the non-sustainability of the country's public debt as well as depletion of the external reserve by government to finance persistent deficit budget. Ogunlana (2005) in fact, management of Nigeria's external debt has been a major macroeconomic problem especially since the early 1980s while a number of reasons account for Nigeria's inability to manage her debts and accelerate economic growth and development including the deteriorating commodity prices and the Dutch Disease, inappropriate economic policies, poor debt management, unfavorable terms of borrowing and the depreciation in currencies in which debt is expressed (Fosu & Agbemavor, 2015). This is why lamented that some Sub-Saharan African countries have continued to face debt service problem fueled by external shocks such as worsening terms of trade, civil strife, absence of sustained adjustment and implementation of structural reforms, lack of proper debt management policies in debtor countries, improper management of currency composition of external debt, and ill lending policies of many creditors (Suma & Adebawale, 2020).

Theoretical Framework

Dependency theory

This study employed dependency theory which was pioneered by Raymond Leslie Buell in 1925. The dependency theory is a popular theory within the social sciences used to explain economic development of states. It is the result of an extensive search to find a theoretical framework to sufficiently analyze and explain both development and underdevelopment within the international system and does so by allowing scholars and practitioners to look to external matters such as politics, economics, and culture, and attempt to come to an understanding of how these issues influence development policies conceptualize the theory as a systematically subordinated status in relations with other states or actors, usually starting economically but with implications in other spheres of activity (Romaniuk, 2017, Igwe O, et al., 2007). It is his view that dependency defines a situation in which the policy of life of a state and its citizens are exploitatively determined by an outside power or powers,

usually through the simultaneous application of unequal socioeconomic, political and cultural measures, and it often occurs either as a successor policy to past unequal ties, or through the acquiescence of the local agents of the foreign power who for various reasons become willing tools of such a policy. Thus, both agree to the fact that dependency is a lingering part-consequence of colonialism and a syndrome of the neo-colonial system, with the mainly third world countries as unequal actors within the Western-dominated international capitalist system (Igwe & Udenigwe, 2010). The obvious implication is that the relationship between the centre and the periphery is unequal. This explains why Scholars argues succinctly that dependence and imperialism results if the periphery is without adequate economic means to challenge foreign monopolies (Udenigwe, 2010). However, it is pertinent to point out that the Dependency Theory was developed in the late 1950s under the guidance of the Director of the United Nations Economic Commission for Latin America, Raul Prebisch. Prebisch and his colleagues were troubled by the fact that economic growth in the advanced industrialized countries did not necessarily lead to growth in the poorer countries. It originated with two papers published in 1949 – one by Hans Singer, the other by Raul Prebisch – in which the authors observed that the terms of trade for underdeveloped countries relative to the developed countries had deteriorated overtime because of the exploitative nature of the relationship between the two worlds. It is a central contention of dependency theory that poor states are impoverished and rich ones enriched by the way poor states are integrated into the worlds system (Agubamah, 2014).

The theory attempts to explain the present underdeveloped state of many nations in the world by examining the patterns of interactions among nations and by arguing that inequality among nations is an intrinsic part of those interactions and agree that dependency characterizes the international system as comprised of two sets of states, variously described as dominant/dependent, center/periphery or metropolitan/satellite where the dominant states are the advanced industrial nations in the Organization of Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) and the dependent states represent those states of Latin America, Asia, and Africa which have low per capita Gross National Products and which rely heavily on the export of a single commodity for foreign exchange earnings (Romaniuk et al., 2017, Ferraro et al., 2008). Dependency theory, according to them, holds that external forces are critical in terms of economic activity of dependent states and those relationships, based on strongly historical patterns and dynamics (i.e., internationalization of capitalism), between dominant and dependent states are a vibrant process, with exchanges taking place between the states playing a considerable role in the reinforcement of patterns of inequality.

By and large, the dependency theory, according to Prebisch arose as a reaction to modernization theory, an earlier theory of development which held that all societies progress through similar stages of development, that today's underdeveloped areas are thus in a similar situation to that of today's developed areas at some time in the past, and that therefore the task in helping the underdeveloped areas out of poverty is to accelerate them along this supposed common path of development, by various means such as investment, technology transfer, and close integration into the world market.

In connection of this theory to this present study, it is yet to be proven that Chinese generosity by way of trade is actually bringing about development in Nigeria, consequent upon the fact that it has not enabled the citizens to use their creative potentials to constantly improve on their impoverished condition using locally-sourced solutions. At best, it remains a one-sided relationship that was not initially and genuinely crafted to lift Nigeria out of underdevelopment trap. But it has, instead, dimmed the prospects of transparency and elevated corruption to a ridiculous level, thus frustrating the vision of achieving economic development in the country. .

Empirical Review

Opusunju (2020) investigated the China-Nigeria trade relations and its effect on the economic growth of Nigeria. The study employed the ex-post facto research design. The study used time series data and data are presented on appendix A and appendix B. The study used reports from the Central Bank of Nigeria for secondary data. The reason for obtaining data from the Central Bank of Nigeria bulletin is that it is very authentic and unique. The study employed various procedures in analyzing the data ranging from measurement of variables, descriptive statistics, spurious regression, correlation matrix, unit root test, co-integration, and Vector Error Correction Model.

The result of findings revealed that causality runs from the export of goods from Nigeria to China to a real gross domestic product which implies that export from Nigeria to China affect the gross domestic

product in Nigeria. The export of goods and services affected the real gross domestic products in Nigeria. The reason is that it increases economies of scale, increased revenue and profit, increased productivity, spreading risk base of business, new product ideas, and tax advantages which eventually added to the gross domestic product in Nigeria.

In accordance with present study, the researcher stated that corruption affects export from Nigeria to China in Nigeria. The nature of corruption in Nigeria affected the export of goods from Nigeria to China in Nigeria. The reason is that corruption does not allow Nigerian to engage fully in export and discovered what they can export best to China. Corruption made Nigeria over other areas of absolute and comparative advantages such as agriculture and mining and concentrated in oil and gas.

Ebere (2019) carried study on the Nigeria-China economic Relations and the contemporary challenges. The study made use of the ex-post facto research design. The secondary method of data collection was used for the study. The result of this study indicated that contrary to the allusion that the Foreign Direct Investment from China has not contributed to the development of Africa, much of such investments have remained a catalyst for promoting infrastructure development, employment generation and revenue generation in the continent through payment of taxes by Chinese industries operating in Africa, while also contributing to its Gross Domestic Product aggregates.

In relation to present study, the researcher stated that China has been accused of “debt-trap diplomacy” that is, of saddling countries with high interest debt that they are unable to repay, giving China leverage over the borrowing country. In a speech in May 2019, Secretary of State Mike Pompeo criticized China for peddling “corrupt infrastructure deals in exchange for political influence,” and using “bribe-fueled debt-trap diplomacy” to undermine good governance in Nigeria.

Mhaka and Jeke (2018) conducted study on the impact of the real exchange rate, market size and economic size on the trade flows between South Africa and China, applying the gravity model of trade. Time series data for the period of 1995–2014 have been used and a multiple linear regression model was employed to study the variables and the ordinary least squares method was used. The explanatory variables consist of the product of South Africa's gross domestic product (GDP) and China's GDP, which act as the proxy for economic size, the product of South Africa's population and China's population, which act as the proxy for market size, and the real exchange rate between SA and China.

The findings of the study revealed that the economic size and the market size have a strong positive impact on trade flows between South Africa and China. On the other hand, the real exchange rate have negative impact on trade flows between South Africa and China.

In connection to this present study, the above study variables used South Africa and China but similar studies can use Nigeria and China to study trade relations and economic growth in Nigeria. The above study failed to include 2011-2020 in their study but this present study included these periods in the study.

Enrico & Marcello (2011) estimated some econometric relations between economic growth and trade/openness, with the addition of control variables (such as the gross fixed capital formation). They used a panel data model for the two countries, to be estimated with fixed effects; to test for reverse causality, they re-estimated the fixed effects model by 2SLS (with the inclusion of specific instrumental variables). The effect on economic growth (in terms of GDP per capita) of our variables of interest Openness and FDI remains positive and statistically significant in all specifications. The results prove the positive growth effects, for the two countries, of opening up and integrating into the world economy.

The above study failed to indicate the two countries that the study addressed this study. The period of study was not stated in the study. The use of panel regression is inappropriate for the study. The study could have used regression and other advanced regression to study the variables.

Babatunde, Jonathan and Muhyideen (2017) examined the impact of international trade on economic growth in Nigeria. They used time series secondary data obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria, the National Bureau of Statistics and International Financial Statistics for a period between 1981 and 2014. Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test together with Phillip Perron (PP) test of Unit Root Tests was employed to ascertain the stationary properties of the variables. The Ordinary Least Square (OLS) technique was used to test for the significant relationship between the level of economic growth proxies by GDP as a dependent variable and exchange rate, government expenditure, interest rate, foreign direct investment, import and export as independent variables.

The result revealed that government expenditures, interest rates, imports, and export are all positively significant while the exchange rate and foreign direct investment are negatively insignificant to the economic growth in Nigeria. The above study is very current and similar studies can also use it but make reference to China –Nigeria economic relations. The study can also include 2011-2020 since the previous study did not address the period.

Lawal and Kamtochukwu (2017) carried studies on the impact of international trade on economic growth. Variables used in the measurement of international trade include Imports, exports, the balance of trade and trade openness while the real gross domestic product was used as a measure for economic growth using periodic data from the years 1985-2015. The econometric tests employed were Unit Root Test, Johansen Co-integration Test and Vector Error Correction Model (VECM). The result showed that there is a long-run relationship between international trade and economic growth, import and trade openness are both insignificant in the short run but significant in the long run while export and balance of trade are significant in both the short and long run. The granger causality test showed that economic growth is independent of imports, exports, and balance of trade but economic growth is unidirectional with trade openness.

Abiodun and Adeolu (2006) carried out a study on trade policy research and training programmes. The studies make use of ex-post factor research design. The secondary method of data collection was used for the study.

The result of the study showed that the Chinese FDI inflow to Nigeria have been on the increase in recent years. A tenfold increase on the flow of Chinese FDI into Nigeria between 1999 and 2006 was recorded. Compare to other sources of FDI inflow to Nigeria, Chinese FDI inflows are in the range of about 0.13% of the total flow of FDI in 2006.

In the area of trade relations, similar recent upsurge was captured by the available data and process of information.

Nigeria export to China is dominated by crude oil to the tune of about 95%. In term of relative share of market, China constitutes only about 1.5 % of the value export in 2000 and 2005.

Nigerian import from China is more diversified than the imports. The observed structure of trade pattern is inconsistency with the Nigeria's quest to export manufactured or finished products.

Tajudeen (2013) conducted a study on Nigeria-China trade relations and implication on the Nigeria domestic economy. The study adopted with little modification the "global competitiveness 2009-2010" model and data as the basis of comparison between Nigeria and China.

In his findings, he stated that there is a trade imbalance between Nigeria and China in favour of the Chinese due to high rate of export to Nigeria with little imports from Nigeria. The trade imbalance notwithstanding, Nigeria stand to gain a lot from Chinese model of growth, investment and manufacturing expertise. Hence, Nigeria government should impose tariff on China's goods in order to allow a level playing ground with Nigeria manufacturers.

Adetoye (2015) studied the impact of international Trade on Economic Growth in Nigeria (1988-2012), using net exports and balance of payment to determine how the international trade impact on the gross domestic product for the economic growth.

The variable used was, total import, total export, gross domestic product, and balance of payment.

The finding shows that import has negative impact on the economic and export is the main factor, which produced great output, and international trade plays an important role in economic growth of Nigeria.

Arodoye and Ayola (2014) studied the nexus between international trade and economic growth in Nigeria by the use of quarterly time series data of GDP at constant prices for the period of 1981-2010. The OLS results indicated that there is a stable, long-run relationship between international trade and economic growth. Conclusively, they discovered, that trade policies which are in favour of export expansion should be encouraged because exports are driver of economic growth.

The above study is unique since it is current and similar studies can be studied to include 2011-2020. The study created impact but failed to indicate pre and post-analysis of China-Nigeria economic relations.

Gap in Literature

The core gap in literature identified from the reviewed previous researchers and scholarly submissions, ideas and works is that most available literature were highly concerned with the China-Africa economic relations but this present study concentrated basically on the trade and its impacts on

socio-economic development in Nigeria, 2015-2022 so as to ascertain how the two countries relate on trade and its impacts in the socio-economic development in Nigeria. Several researches have been conducted to determine or establish the linkage between Nigeria-China economic relations such as (Donnes, 2018; Donnelley, 2018; Shattack. 2018, Mulaku & Lemmy, 2019; Akinrinde, 2020; & Igwe (2020), among others. The general thinking of these scholars reveals that, the dynamic of bilateral economic relation between Nigeria and China over the years had been accompanied with some criticisms, accusations, connotations and denotations as it relates to trade, investment, economy, national economy, cultural factors, among others, which many viewed the relation as having one side effect and lopsided. These studies are plausible in their own rights. However, based on the previous works reviewed some limitations were noticed on the research questions which is different from the present study. Therefore, based on the above limitations have come to fill the gap study.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study used mixed research design which is the combination of qualitative and quantitative approach to collect and analyze data (Creswell & Tashakkori, 2007). The data generated for this study was analyzed using textual method of data analysis.

DATA ANALYSIS

Impact of Nigeria-China Trade Relations

Imbalance of Trade

Political scholars have noticed that Nigeria-China relations have a negative trade balance over time, with favours moving toward the Chinese area. Indeed, as Azaiki (2006) puts it, the Nigeria-China relationship is one in which raw resources are delivered to China and completed products are imported from the same; It is one in which features of western exploitation are present, but in more sophisticated and lethal ways. The trade deficit will worsen as China attempts to build its African trade surplus in order to counter hefty imports from developed countries. As a result, there is a noticeable resolve on the part of the Chinese to offset their trade deficit with the West by attempting to sustain trade supplies with non-Western trading partners. Furthermore, African countries' trade regimes remain post-colonial, with little effort being made to fundamentally modify the situation. This is why Africa's trade with China has remained negative.

In addition to commercial investment, Onuoha (2008) claims that China has entered into weaponry deals with African nations as a form of foreign policy. China does not share the same worries about human rights as the United States and Europe. As a result, she is willing to sell military equipment and weapons to almost anyone. Indeed, Beijing sees Africa as a potential growth market for its military equipment. China's active discovery of African oil supplies necessitates the need for security surrounding them, prompting Beijing to dispatch Chinese military trainers to assist their African counterparts. This implies that Africa will continue to be a hotbed of war and catastrophe for the foreseeable future. It also runs counter to the African Union's efforts to reduce the spread or proliferation of small guns in the area. Political insecurity, military resurgence, militancy, and poverty are the results.

Many Nigerians are out of job; unemployment gives rise to societal crimes that China is worried about. Though some can argue that there are now Chinese companies operating in Nigeria, the problem is whose interests are the companies protecting? Not Nigeria's of course. Thousands of Chinese in Nigeria came with visitor's visa; the type that should not allow them to work in the country. But what happens? These visiting Chinese are shielded by the Chinese companies and given jobs meant for Nigerians. In China, Nigerians are languishing in prisons for violating basic immigration laws; Nigeria is different; each Chinese in Nigeria is an expatriate that must be shielded at times with the connivance of the Nigerian immigration service.

Maltreatment of Nigerian Workers and Non-fulfillment of Trade Agreement

Nigerian workers are mistreated by their Chinese employers. There have been numerous cases of these workers being mistreated. For example the two Chinese who own and operate Oceanic Bakeries in Wuse district of Abuja were arrested for abusing the rights of Nigerians working in their bakery (Ezeobi, 2016). A circumstance in which Nigerian workers were trapped like animals beside an oven in the bakery and were compelled, when thirsty, to beg their Chinese manager, who would not allow

them out to drink water, unveils the harsh and dehumanizing conditions to which Nigerian workers are subjected by their foreign employers in major commercial cities of Nigeria Chinese firms also fail to check environmental compliance, participate in corruption schemes, and allow for multiple infringement of African workers' rights (Egbula&Zheng, 2011)..

The Chinese government are willing to increase profits by whatever means necessary, while partnering with authoritarian regimes and accepting lack of democracy and violations of human rights. This raises concerns about the Nigerian government's ability to adopt – and enforce – proper labour laws and perform frequent workplace inspections. In regards to the technological transfer, it has been discovered that China has refused to transfer technology to Nigeria because during the infrastructure building, China bring more of their people to partner and build what they had to build in Nigeria rather than few Chinese workers and more of local workers (Ogunkola&Adewiyi, 2008). Also they have refused because they know that by employing local workers and paying them, they are only increasing the economic growth of Nigeria and having loss instead they employ more of their people and pay them thereby increasing their own economy growth. China is only prepared to launch Nigeria's satellite to the orbit after paying some fees. The scientists remain Chinese working in China. The scientific template is Chinese and the Asian Monarch is least prepared to reveal or teach Nigeria the modalities. Nigeria's quest for a technological transfer through China therefore remains a dream and the foremost contemporary challenge in the Sino-Nigerian relation (Adigbuo, 2021).

Dumping Due to China Trade Policy

When a country or corporation exports a product, the price in the foreign importing market is lower than the price in the exporter's local market. Dumping is a type of pricing discrimination. It occurs when a manufacturer lowers the price of an item entering a foreign market to a level below what domestic buyers in the original country pay. The behavior is thought to be deliberate in order to get a competitive advantage in the importing market. The nature of Nigeria-Chinese relations frequently allows large quantities of low-cost, low-quality, and inferior goods to enter Nigeria's economy (Ogunsanwo, 2008). This not only threatens and displaces Nigerian industries, but it also effectively displaces workers from such industries, resulting in unemployment and limiting people's ability to afford healthy and nutritious food (Campbell, 2011). The growing threat of product dumping from Asian countries, particularly China, into the Nigerian market are gravely damaging the competitiveness of the country's already troubled manufacturing industry. China's skyrocketing population of 1.6 billion requires new industrial products trading channels, and Nigeria, the most populous black nation with a large capacity to readily absorb many of these items, is an obvious target for Chinese officials (Galaju&Tofan, 2020).

Substandard Products or Services

Many Chinese products sold in Nigeria are counterfeit, inferior, and of poor quality. Though Nigerians continue to patronize them, maybe due to inelastic demand for inexpensive goods (cheap items are usually of poor quality); this is a concern that China must address or risk losing a major share of the Nigerian market as national income per person rises. While many blame the Nigerian government for failing to crack down on such goods, others point the finger at Nigerian businessmen and women who import such goods while knowing they are of poor quality. .Regardless of the situation, China and Nigeria must collaborate to add value. Medication that is substandard or faked poses a substantial threat to world health. In low- and middle-income nations, nearly one out of every five anti-malarial is poor or fraudulent.

China's agricultural investment in Nigeria is insignificant in comparison to her investment in other sectors of the Nigerian economy. China's initial investments in Nigeria's oil and manufacturing sectors were largely motivated by the need to secure essential minerals for the country's economic growth. As a result of this situation, capital has continued to flow into more exploitative sectors, resulting in a gradual neglect of less exploitative ones, such as agriculture (Daniel &Maiwada, 2015; Manji, 2008). Furthermore, Chinese companies' attitudes toward Nigerian development are skewed because they prefer to repatriate profits earned in Nigeria to their home countries. China was just concerned and focused on the oil production aspect of Nigeria, neglecting the agricultural sector making Nigeria's economy to only depend on oil exportation. Nigeria, which was once reliant on agricultural, moved its priority to oil exports in the 1970s, and decades of weak economic progress later, there is a need to refocus on agriculture.

The politics of Nigeria-China trade relations

With just a meager 9 percent overall fertile land, China's formidability exemplified in her agricultural and food policies has afforded her the capacity to feed about 20 percent of the global population. Similarly, China was able to successfully utilize the agrarian sector in its quest for development (Udoh, 2014). Chinese policy recommendations combined with skills acquisition, knowledge transfer, and training could prove effective in controlling the direction of farmers' practices to strengthen overall production, organization, and consumption of food (Angelou, 2016). Notably, from 2007 to 2009 China supplied 104 personnel experienced in the agricultural sector to 33 African countries, including Nigeria, for technical aid and training in the building of agricultural plants (Daniel & Maiwada, 2015). African countries, including Nigeria, also received about 500 agricultural personnel from China for training in 2009 – the training covered matters on economic development of suburbs, food productivity, proper utilization of agricultural technology, and so on (Sun, 2011).

The relations with China have helped to secure access to financing aimed at revamping Nigeria's agricultural sector and overall food production. For example, the China-Exim Bank has funded the development of sophisticated cassava flour plants in Nigeria (Ubi, 2019). Also, in January 2018, Chinese investors announced their intention to invest huge amounts into the energy, agriculture, and infrastructural sectors (Adepegba, 2018). Nigeria became the second-highest beneficiary of Chinese FDI after South Africa between 2003 and 2009 (Egbula & Zheng, 2011).

Bilateral trade relations between Nigeria and China have opened huge trade doors to Nigeria. For instance, China has shown increasing interest in the agricultural produce of Africa, particularly Nigeria, e.g., in her cassava products. This trade deal has made the Nigerian government invest huge amounts into the agricultural sector and various programs to meet up with China's cassava demand (Ubi, 2019). In terms of cassava exports to China, Nigeria is ranked first. Interestingly, China as the world's largest purchaser of cassava ultimately provides a lucrative market for Nigeria. According to Sun (2011), Nigeria exports about 5,000 tons of cassava to China on an annual basis.

Another area wherein China trade is having positive impact on Nigeria is in the Infrastructural Development. Chinese companies have helped in lots of infrastructural development across the region of Nigeria. They have been involved in hydro-dams and thermal stations construction, construction of stadium, railway, road networks, and airport among others. Most importantly, these projects are partly or totally funded by the Chinese government (Wang, 2012). One of such is the \$8.3 billion project to rebuild the derelict railway between Lagos and Kano, and the first stage of the Nigeria 20-year rail modernization plan (White, 2006). Others are investment of \$6 billion in railways, oil refinery and power in exchange for rights to drill oil in Nigeria by Chinese Oil and Natural Gas Corporation and Indian multi-national company L. N. Mittal (Bello, 2017). This implies that Nigeria is benefitting in these investment and also in opportunity of technology transfer in line with the local content regulations.

In terms of Chinese Private Enterprises which has been opened by the China economic reforms including the 1985 no-restriction investment, the Chinese private investors' have trade activities cut across small, medium scale and multi-national firms in Nigeria. Example of such is the Hashan Corporation from Eastern Zhejiang Province that has \$6 million investment in local shoe making industry. Also, Huawei Company, a telecommunication giant has investment of more than \$1 billion in Sub-Sahara Africa economy, Nigeria inclusive (Wang, 2012).

Moreover, the informal sector also benefitted in the increasing Chinese private enterprises participation in Nigeria economy. It is on record that more Chinese restaurant, electronics and appliances shops, consumables, and "China Towns" are built in many parts of Nigeria major cities (Tull, 2006). A case study of Lagos where three China commercial villages, trading in consumables, household utensils and textile imported from China, is worthy of mentioning.

In the case of the China Win-Win Principle, (Pang, 2003 in Taylor, 2004) informed that the principle offer a mutual benefits for China and Nigeria. This, according to him is characterized by Chinese company's payment of compensation and carrying out local development such as borehole drilling, street tarring, school renovation whenever a project is to be done. Not only this, the principle enable ease of access of Nigerian exported products into the Chinese market and vice-versa. This principle has been argued to stimulate partnership between businesses in these countries in the area of agriculture, technology and infrastructural development (Agubamah, 2014). This principle need to be explored further by companies in Nigeria and African at large for the development of the country.

General Impacts of Nigeria-China Trade Relations

The challenges confronting Nigeria-China relations and socio-economic development in Nigeria were lack of coherent policies towards China; poor policy implementation; poor use of ICT in business, economic and trade; lack of patriotism on the part of Nigeria leadership; corruption; lack of capital and grants on the part of entrepreneur; lack of government support to manufacturers; poor knowledge of existing opportunities and lack of cooperation between the business men of both countries. This agrees with all literature consulted (Umo-Udo, 2018). The foregoing analysis of the Sino-Nigeria relations has revealed so far that despite its shortcomings and adverse effects on the economy of Nigeria, it has somewhat proven to be an effective and formidable co-operation after all. However, most of the adverse effects which this relationship embeds would be discussed here.

First and foremost policies adopted by Nigeria policy makers do not have the strongest possible impact on the country's long-term economic growth and therefore rarely benefit the majority of her citizens. Utomi (2017) had already noted, by 2011, that while many of the on-going policies being pursued were likely to benefit Nigeria and significantly contribute to economic development in some areas, the strategies seem to neglect essential long-term needs, important segments of the population and the targeting of essential sectors that would lead to an undiversified economy. This assessment remains current in China-Nigeria relations. One evidence of this were the farmlands sold out to Chinese without taking cognizance of the nation's population growth in the nearest future nor her needs for self-sufficiency both now and in future.

The issue of quality of products has also been another albatross for the development of China-Nigeria relationship. The flooding of Nigeria with sub-standard Chinese goods has become alarming that the Standard Organization of Nigeria (SON) threatened the Chinese that they would report them to the World Trade Organization (WTO) should the proliferation of inferior goods in Nigeria persist. On their part, however, the Chinese government maintained that Nigerian importers often pressure Chinese suppliers to produce low quality products in order to make them affordable for Nigerians, but more importantly for the purposes of profit maximization by the importers (WTO, 2020). It has been argued that even if this claim was true, the integrity of the Chinese suppliers was also questionable after as recent developments led to complaints against the poor service delivery of the Chinese-owned media outlet Star Times.

Evidences have suggested that Nigeria is drastically underperforming in spite of the strong revenue flows from high priced crude oil exports. Various bureaucratic obstacles and a lack of strong institutions have led to constrained progress in areas of infrastructure, agriculture and technological transfer (Orifa, 2018). Similarly, widespread corruption has made the transfer of wealth to the lower classes difficult and has shifted Foreign Direct Investment from the non-petroleum sector. Until Nigeria can develop credible, accountable and transparent institutions, a free-market system that encourages investments, diversification and competition is unlikely to emerge. Like the situation with Western-owned oil companies, the exploration of oil in Nigeria by Chinese companies have often led to pollution and environmental degradation, among others, causing local inhabitants in the oil-producing areas to resort to conventional ways of solving such problems, largely by insurgency (Tuomi, 2011). Insurgency in itself constitutes another debacle to the growth of Nigeria-China relationship by rendering the work area unsafe.

Language barriers and cultural differences weigh heavily against the transfer of technological skills from Chinese to Nigerian citizens and because cheap Chinese labour is often used, skills needed for large industrial products are rarely transferred to local African population (Udeala, 2013). In addition, little success has been achieved in the aspect of development of Nigerian entrepreneurs. While Nigerian businessmen have learned to export successfully by using Chinese models and have profited by partnering in joint ventures with Chinese, just relatively small and educated elite have been the primary beneficiaries of this (Tuomi, 2011). Most Nigerian businessmen continue to face language and cultural barriers. Even the few beneficiaries are just at the bottom of the chain and the Chinese at the apex. Correspondingly, the latter profit more than the former in virtually all business transactions. In these relations, Nigeria's officials have made China's engagement a priority, the strongest leadership has been observed on the Chinese side. Nigerians, in particular, have dictated to the Chinese which development projects they would like to undertake, but the absence of true leaders on the Nigerian side who are capable of articulating and enforcing a long-term development strategy that adequately addresses the needs of majority of Nigerian citizen's remains a key challenge (Jauch,

2011). Nigeria's rampant corruption has also proved to be a serious economic obstacle that must be overcome if Nigeria is to successfully leverage its demands vis-à-vis China.

Table 1: Showing China Exports to Nigeria in 2022

China Exports to Nigeria	Value	Year
<u>Electrical, electronic equipment</u>	\$2.91B	2022
<u>Machinery, nuclear reactors, boilers</u>	\$2.28B	2022
<u>Articles of iron or steel</u>	\$1.49B	2022
<u>Plastics</u>	\$1.40B	2022
<u>Vehicles other than railway, tramway</u>	\$1.34B	2022
<u>Manmade filaments</u>	\$1.32B	2022
<u>Articles of apparel, not knit or crocheted</u>	\$956.44M	2022
<u>Iron and steel</u>	\$817.48M	2022
<u>Footwear, gaiters and the like,</u>	\$747.47M	2022
<u>Furniture, lighting signs, prefabricated buildings</u>	\$736.91M	2022
<u>Bird skin, feathers, artificial flowers, human hair</u>	\$727.41M	2022
<u>Aluminum</u>	\$601.28M	2022
<u>Cotton</u>	\$559.23M	2022
<u>Ceramic products</u>	\$549.16M	2022
<u>Miscellaneous chemical products</u>	\$471.11M	2022
<u>Rubbers</u>	\$468.40M	2022
<u>Articles of apparel, knit or crocheted</u>	\$423.11M	2022
<u>Organic chemicals</u>	\$340.61M	2022
<u>Manmade staple fibers</u>	\$337.35M	2022
<u>Miscellaneous articles of base metal</u>	\$312.56M	2022
<u>Knitted or crocheted fabric</u>	\$290.07M	2022
<u>Special woven or tufted fabric, lace, tapestry</u>	\$238.56M	2022
<u>Wood and articles of wood, wood charcoal</u>	\$233.72M	2022
<u>Articles of leather, animal gut, harness, travel good</u>	\$215.08M	2022
<u>Miscellaneous manufactured articles</u>	\$193.79M	2022
<u>Pharmaceutical products</u>	\$186.95M	2022
<u>Optical, photo, technical, medical apparatus</u>	\$175.96M	2022
<u>Impregnated, coated or laminated textile fabric</u>	\$159.80M	2022
<u>Paper and paperboard, articles of pulp, paper and board</u>	\$157.18M	2022
<u>Inorganic chemicals, precious metal compound, isotope</u>	\$147.21M	2022
<u>Other made textile articles, sets, worn clothing</u>	\$139.62M	2022
<u>Tools, implements, cutlery of base metal</u>	\$132.21M	2022
<u>Pearls, precious stones, metals, coins</u>	\$107.58M	2022
<u>Tanning, dyeing extracts, tannins, derivatives, pigments</u>	\$105.04M	2022
<u>Miscellaneous edible preparations</u>	\$102.40M	2022
<u>Wadding, felt, nonwovens, yarns, twine, cordage</u>	\$90.74M	2022
<u>Glass and glassware</u>	\$89.52M	2022
<u>Toys, games, sports requisites</u>	\$86.52M	2022
<u>Soaps, lubricants, waxes, candles, modeling pastes</u>	\$71.83M	2022
<u>Albuminoids, modified starches, glues, enzymes</u>	\$57.52M	2022
<u>Essential oils, perfumes, cosmetics, toiletries</u>	\$52.84M	2022
<u>Railway, tramway locomotives, rolling stock, equipment</u>	\$50.60M	2022

China Exports to Nigeria	Value	Year
<u>Fertilizers</u>	\$50.50M	2022
<u>Vegetable, fruit, nut food preparations</u>	\$47.91M	2022
<u>Printed books, newspapers, pictures</u>	\$42.28M	2022
<u>Headgear and</u>	\$39.80M	2022
<u>Stone, plaster, cement, asbestos, mica or similar materials</u>	\$34.13M	2022
<u>Copper</u>	\$22.48M	2022
<u>Umbrellas, walking-sticks, seat-sticks, whips</u>	\$22.19M	2022
<u>Sugars and sugar confectionery</u>	\$18.62M	2022
<u>Carpets and other textile floor coverings</u>	\$14.48M	2022
<u>Meat, fish and seafood preparations</u>	\$12.81M	2022
<u>Fish, crustaceans, molluscs, aquatic invertebrates</u>	\$12.15M	2022
<u>Musical instruments, parts and accessories</u>	\$11.62M	2022
<u>Photographic or cinematographic goods</u>	\$11.57M	2022
<u>Clocks and watches</u>	\$9.79M	2022
<u>Wool, animal hair, horsehair yarn and fabric</u>	\$7.59M	2022
<u>Salt, sulphur, earth, stone, plaster, lime and cement</u>	\$6.65M	2022
<u>Mineral fuels, oils, distillation products</u>	\$6.25M	2022
<u>Milling products, malt, starches, inlin, wheat gluten</u>	\$4.70M	2022
<u>Cereal, flour, starch, milk preparations and products</u>	\$4.61M	2022
<u>Pulp of wood, fibrous cellulosic material, waste</u>	\$4.11M	2022
<u>Base metals not specified elsewhere, cermets.</u>	\$3.37M	2022
<u>Explosives, pyrotechnics, matches, pyrophorics</u>	\$3.11M	2022
<u>Aircraft, spacecraft</u>	\$3.02M	2022
<u>Residues, wastes of food industry, animal fodder</u>	\$2.92M	2022
<u>Ships, boats, and other floating structures</u>	\$2.88M	2022
<u>Commodities not specified according to kind</u>	\$2.80M	2022
<u>Coffee, tea, mate and spices</u>	\$2.64M	2022
<u>Tin</u>	\$1.98M	2022
<u>Lac, gums, resins</u>	\$1.94M	2022
<u>Cocoa and cocoa preparations</u>	\$1.70M	2022
<u>Beverages, spirits and vinegar</u>	\$1.58M	2022
<u>Arms and ammunition, parts and accessories</u>	\$1.41M	2022
<u>Tobacco and manufactures tobacco substitutes</u>	\$1.24M	2022
<u>Zinc</u>	\$1.18M	2022
<u>Edible vegetables and certain roots and tubers</u>	\$1.09M	2022
<u>Animal, vegetable fats and oils, cleavage products</u>	\$869.77K	2022
<u>Oil seed, oleagic fruits, grain, seed, fruits</u>	\$378.70K	2022
<u>Dairy products, eggs, honey, edible products</u>	\$288.04K	2022
<u>Raw hides and skins (other than furskins) and leather</u>	\$235.34K	2022
<u>Nickel</u>	\$201.81K	2022
<u>Ores slag and ash</u>	\$185.35K	2022
<u>Cereals</u>	\$173.52K	2022
<u>Manufacturers of plaiting material, basketwork</u>	\$109.19K	2022
<u>Vegetable textile fibers not specified elsewhere, paper yarn, woven fabric</u>	\$65.82K	2022

China Exports to Nigeria	Value	Year
<u>Edible fruits, nuts, peel of citrus fruit, melons</u>	\$62.24K	2022
<u>Live trees, plants, bulbs, roots, cut flowers</u>	\$42.1K	2022
<u>Works of art, collectors' pieces and antiques</u>	\$17.22K	2022
<u>Lead</u>	\$14.40K	2022
<u>Silk</u>	\$11.81K	2022
<u>Furskins and artificial fur, manufactures</u>	\$11.37K	2022
<u>Products of animal origin</u>	\$4.94K	2022

Source: Okoye, 2022.

Table 1 showed China exports to Nigeria in 2022, in spite of the functional trade relationship between Nigeria and China, the benefits from the socio-economic development interaction between the two countries have been subjected to diverse opinions by scholars and analysts, in which Chinese exports and investments in Nigeria attracted resentment and criticisms. Concerns have been raised specifically over the impact of Chinese trade activities in Nigeria's socio-economic development, which is substantially affected by the dumping of inferior Chinese industrial products into the country, lack of technology transfer from China to Nigeria, fewer opportunities for the survival of Nigeria's investments in China, visa and employment restrictions to Nigerians to explore business opportunities in the country (Ogunsanwo, 2018).

Enuka (2010, 11) also argues that the FDI from China has heightened Nigeria's dependence on the Chinese economy, thus undermining its own economic security. Ogunrinu (2017) argues that since the Chinese government initiated the "Go global" strategy for capturing global markets through both public and private Chinese enterprises in 1998, its FDI has been increasing in Africa especially Nigeria through its investment strategies in the continent, which center on building the necessary infrastructure to explore Nigerian oil and gas for China's industrial growth. Mthembu (2021) contends that, contrary to the allusion that the FDI from China has not contributed to the development of Nigeria, much of such investments have remained a catalyst for promoting infrastructure development, employment generation and revenue generation in the continent through payment of taxes by Chinese industries operating in Nigeria, while also contributing to its Gross Domestic Product aggregates. As noted by Mthembu (2021), the breakdown of the trade relations between China and Africa shows that Nigeria has had \$15.42 billion net investments from China, Algeria \$9.23 billion, South Africa \$6.64 billion, Democratic Republic of Congo \$6.55 billion, Niger \$5.26 billion, Egypt \$3.23 billion, Libya \$2.28 billion, Zambia \$2.49 billion, Sudan \$2.210 billion, Ethiopia \$1.9 billion, among others. A critical check on this trade relationship shows imbalance of trade to the disfavor of African countries that exchanges their low value added products at far lesser prices with industrial products from China with higher foreign exchange earnings for the latter.

Table: 2 Showing Nigeria Exports to China in 2021

Nigeria Exports to China	Value	Year
<u>Mineral fuels, oils, distillation products</u>	\$1.47B	2021
<u>Oil seed, oleagic fruits, grain, seed, fruits</u>	\$140.88M	2021
<u>Ores slag and ash</u>	\$58.55M	2021
<u>Aluminum</u>	\$47.75M	2021
<u>Copper</u>	\$33.88M	2021
<u>Glass and glassware</u>	\$27.06M	2021
<u>Ships, boats, and other floating structures</u>	\$19.81M	2021
<u>Animal, vegetable fats and oils, cleavage products</u>	\$13.46M	2021
<u>Rubbers</u>	\$5.07M	2021
<u>Raw hides and skins (other than furskins) and leather</u>	\$4.08M	2021
<u>Live trees, plants, bulbs, roots, cut flowers</u>	\$3.72M	2021
<u>Inorganic chemicals, precious metal compound, isotope</u>	\$3.29M	2021

Nigeria Exports to China	Value	Year
<u>Salt, sulphur, earth, stone, plaster, lime and cement</u>	\$3.14M	2021
<u>Cocoa and cocoa preparations</u>	\$3.11M	2021
<u>Machinery, nuclear reactors, boilers</u>	\$1.82M	2021
<u>Coffee, tea, mate and spices</u>	\$882.18K	2021
<u>Wood and articles of wood, wood charcoal</u>	\$738.00K	2021
<u>Products of animal origin</u>	\$630.04K	2021
<u>Cotton</u>	\$526.27K	2021
<u>Lead</u>	\$445.86K	2021
<u>Edible fruits, nuts, peel of citrus fruit, melons</u>	\$346.66K	2021
<u>Miscellaneous chemical products</u>	\$341.00K	2021
<u>Stone, plaster, cement, asbestos, mica or similar materials</u>	\$313.35K	2021
<u>Bird skin, feathers, artificial flowers, human hair</u>	\$168.07K	2021
<u>Meat and edible meat offal</u>	\$152.66K	2021
<u>Base metals not specified elsewhere, cermets.</u>	\$146.19K	2021
<u>Miscellaneous articles of base metal</u>	\$108.75K	2021
<u>Lac, gums, resins</u>	\$99.86K	2021
<u>Plastics</u>	\$95.45K	2021
<u>Edible vegetables and certain roots and tubers</u>	\$81.54K	2021
<u>Furniture, lighting signs, prefabricated buildings</u>	\$59.96K	2021
<u>Manmade staple fibers</u>	\$55.98K	2021
<u>Zinc</u>	\$38.78K	2021
<u>Knitted or crocheted fabric</u>	\$38.05K	2021
<u>Pearls, precious stones, metals, coins</u>	\$29.24K	2021
<u>Miscellaneous edible preparations</u>	\$23.37K	2021
<u>Organic chemicals</u>	\$22.85K	2021
<u>Iron and steel</u>	\$12.85K	2021
<u>Live animals</u>	\$12.61K	2021
<u>Optical, photo, technical, medical apparatus</u>	\$9.41K	2021
<u>Silk</u>	\$8.47K	2021
<u>Miscellaneous manufactured articles</u>	\$6.9K	2021
<u>Cereal, flour, starch, milk preparations and products</u>	\$5.24K	2021
<u>Milling products, malt, starches, inlin, wheat gluten</u>	\$3.23K	2021
<u>Electrical, electronic equipment</u>	\$398.85K	2019
<u>Beverages, spirits and vinegar</u>	\$197.72K	2019
<u>Fish, crustaceans, molluscs, aquatics invertebrates</u>	\$118.48K	2019
<u>Vegetable, fruit, nut food preparations</u>	\$108.90K	2019
<u>Other made textile articles, sets, worn clothing</u>	\$32.93K	2019
<u>Residues, wastes of food industry, animal fodder</u>	\$16.99K	2019
<u>Clocks and watches</u>	\$13.21K	2019
<u>Pulp of wood, fibrous cellulosic material, waste</u>	\$6.86K	2019
<u>Sugars and sugar confectionery</u>	\$49.88K	2018
<u>Dairy products, eggs, honey, edible products</u>	\$16.83K	2018
<u>Fertilizers</u>	\$16.15K	2018
<u>Soaps, lubricants, waxes, candles, modelling pastes</u>	\$12.62K	2018

Nigeria Exports to China	Value	Year
<u>Ceramic products</u>	\$10.77K	2018
<u>Meat, fish and seafood preparations</u>	\$4.05K	2018
<u>Arms and ammunition, parts and accessories</u>	\$103.16K	2017
<u>Photographic or cinematographic goods</u>	\$272.68K	2016
<u>Articles of iron or steel</u>	\$567	2016
<u>Vehicles other than railway, tramway</u>	\$219.18K	2015
<u>Printed books, newspapers, pictures</u>	\$184.45K	2015
<u>Railway, tramway locomotives, rolling stock, equipment</u>	\$34.46K	2015
<u>Vegetable plaiting materials, vegetable products</u>	\$25.56K	2015
<u>Nickel</u>	\$8.27K	2015
<u>Vegetable textile fibers not specified elsewhere, paper yarn, woven fabric</u>	\$2.19K	2015
<u>Manmade filaments</u>	\$49	2015
<u>Albuminoids, modified starches, glues, enzymes</u>	\$441.32K	2014
<u>Works of art, collectors' pieces and antiques</u>	\$352.71K	2014
<u>Footwear, gaiters and the like,</u>	\$50.30K	2014
<u>Wool, animal hair, horsehair yarn and fabric</u>	\$9.97K	2014
<u>Paper and paperboard, articles of pulp, paper and board</u>	\$1.11K	2014
<u>Cereals</u>	\$6.84M	2013
<u>Explosives, pyrotechnics, matches, pyrophorics</u>	\$172.02K	2013
<u>Essential oils, perfumes, cosmetics, toiletries</u>	\$37.77K	2013
<u>Wadding, felt, nonwovens, yarns, twine, cordage</u>	\$30.30K	2013
<u>Umbrellas, walking-sticks, seat-sticks, whips</u>	\$20.18K	2013
<u>Pharmaceutical products</u>	\$19.25K	2013
<u>Toys, games, sports requisites</u>	\$17.98K	2013
<u>Impregnated, coated or laminated textile fabric</u>	\$14.58K	2013
<u>Special woven or tufted fabric, lace, tapestry</u>	\$13.21K	2013
<u>Musical instruments, parts and accessories</u>	\$6.45K	2013
<u>Tobacco and manufactures tobacco substitutes</u>	\$8.06M	2012
<u>Tin</u>	\$863.63K	2012
<u>Tanning, dyeing extracts, tannins, derivatives, pigments</u>	\$232.98K	2012
<u>Tools, implements, cutlery of base metal</u>	\$101.51K	2012
<u>Aircraft, spacecraft</u>	\$87.57K	2012
<u>Carpets and other textile floor coverings</u>	\$994	2012
<u>Articles of leather, animal gut, harness, travel good</u>	\$3.93M	2011
<u>Articles of apparel, knit or crocheted</u>	\$32.33K	2011
<u>Headgear and</u>	\$15.02K	2011

Source: Okoye, 2022.

Table 2 shows Nigeria exports to China in 2021, as noted by Ian (2022) stated that the core interests of the China-Nigeria relations in the area of trade, exports and industry, in which Nigeria gave generous concessions to the Chinese to establish industries in the country. Ian (2022) also discussed the contemporary drivers of the relationship between the two countries, which revolves around Nigeria's oil in return for China's aid. Despite Ian's attempt to chronicle the major events that occurred in Nigeria-China relations, the work did not exhaust other vital areas of the bilateral relations such as the condition of service of the Nigerian workers in Chinese industries, loans, among others.

Conversely, Nigeria's exports to China are spread over many and varied products, which have been classified according to the Standard International Trade Classification Revision 3 (SITC Rev. 3).

These products include raw food, animal skin, crude oil, chemical products, and manufactured products. Nigeria's total export to China in 2015 was US\$307.3 million, with the main export commodity being oil and lubricants, which represented US\$273.7 million. The next most important export in 2016 was crude materials which totaled US\$33.3 million. The remaining two broad commodities of cocoa and cotton exported to China in 2016 were valued between US\$0.1 million and US\$0.2 million. Thus, in terms of Nigeria's exports to China, oil and lubricants ranked first, followed by beverages and live animals, while manufactured goods rank fourth. In terms of significance of Nigeria's exports to China relative to the world, Nigeria exported more crude materials than any other item, which constituted the main exports of Nigeria to China in 2016.

Impact of Nigeria-China Relations on Infrastructure Development

The role of infrastructure vital for both industrial and technological progression in Nigeria cannot be over-emphasized. As a result of political strife and disregard, infrastructure for example, highway, railroads, hydroelectric power and structures are broken and with the goal for Nigeria to achieve its development objectives, the facilities must recapture full usefulness to satisfy the standard for yielding most extreme efficiency and productivity. For various years, Nigeria has been on the mission to improve her infrastructure sector, however has constantly missed the mark concerning that objective as a result of low internally generated funds and low foreign direct investments. In the transportation business, road networks are restricted and in poor condition, with just 31% of them paved (Nigeria Project Agenda, 2007), which thus denies access to rural areas where most agricultural merchandise are produced (Ochayi, 2009). This difference consequently eases back the process of moving products and services to economic centers.

While trying to address the rail way sector which once worked successfully, the administration of Nigeria has set out on a Railway Recovery Program. A noteworthy milestone in this program was the signing of a \$8.3 billion agreement contract with the Chinese government which included two trenches; the fundamental contract covering the first rail that would connect the country's economic capital Lagos (south) to the biggest business city in the Kano (north), while the second would connection Port Harcourt (south) and Jos (central) and another would link all the 36 states' capitals in Nigeria (Nigeria Project Agenda, 2007) which would be finished up within five years by a Chinese firm (Sanusi, 2013; Gaye, 2007). Nigeria regularly alluded to as the "Giant of Africa" is scarcely satisfying that desire when accessing to her economic performance utilizing economic pointers such as GDP per capita and joblessness rate (Gaye, 2007; Sanusi, 2013).

Nigeria's push to arrive at a concurrence with a Chinese firm on this gigantic railroad venture is to her greatest advantage. The connection of these major urban areas is a solution for Nigeria to reinforce its position on the continent and universally on the grounds that, the working of the railroad system facilitates the easy transportation of products within the nation. Likewise, the presence of this perplexing railroad system will fill in as a model for other African countries while at the same time moving Nigeria into an economic viable country/power. The biggest Chinese construction company in Nigeria, which additionally holds the status of the second biggest construction company firm of any origin is China Civil Engineering Construction Corporation (CCECC) had one of its first Nigerian projects of \$4.8 million to rehabilitate the 71 kilometer Papalanto-Lagos freeway in 2000- 2001; at that point pursued by an increasingly generous contract of \$50.5 million, 5000 unit athletes' town for the eight yearly All-African Games in Abuja finished on August 2003 ((Adeyemo, 2009). CCECC likewise restored the Ikot Akpaden-Okoroette street in 2003-2004 for \$5.7 million; built another \$16.7 million corporate base camp for the Nigerian Communications Commission in Abuja in 2003-2005; and is the principle construction company at the Lekki Free Trade Zone close to Lagos (Mthembu-Salter, 2009).

Another noticeable Chinese construction company active in Nigeria is the China Geo-Engineering Corporation (CGC), which has been available in the nation since the 1980s, when it began off burrowing boreholes to expand Nigerian's fresh water access (Mthembu-Salter, 2009). It has been engaged with various projects, including rehabilitation of Kebbi Airport, rejuvenating a noteworthy water supply venture in Gombe, reconstructing the road from Kano to Maduguri and numerous other littler routes, and the construction of the Sabke Dam (CGC, 2009). Like CCECC, CGC's principle selling point in Nigeria is its price in terms of affordability, however the company has goals to raise

its quality and service provision levels so it can contend on level terms with Germany's Julius Berger, the most dominant construction company in Nigeria, (CGC representative, 2009).

Impact on Control and Dominance of Investment and Projects

There is a belief that China is funding projects in Africa in order to assert control and dominate African countries in the future. China's main aim with foreign investment is geostrategic, not commercial (Mourdoukoutas 2019). There is a belief that China's own commercial and geopolitical interests are maximized when its lending allies are suffering. Chinese policy had the potential of affecting port calls and hub status decisions (Hutson, 2018). Chinese investments in sub-Saharan African ports have been seen to be allegedly posing threats to U.S. influence in sub-Saharan Africa as well as African independence. A CSIS report, *Influence and Infrastructure: The Strategic Stakes of Foreign Projects*, identifies some of the strategic risks posed by the Chinese infrastructure projects; permitting Beijing to possibly limit access to its rivals, exploit ports during conflict, and gather intelligence information (Devermont & Chiang, 2019). There are potential threats, such as the taking over of African ports by the Chinese to the detriment of Africans (Hutson 2018). Dahir (2019), Bavir (2019) and Pandey (2019) cite Sri Lanka's Hambantota Port as a warning account of the dangers of dependence on Chinese loans. It was alleged that Chinese state-owned company took control of the Sri Lankan port of Hambantota at the southern tip of India.

However, some investigations have shown that severe economic factors forced the government to seek out for various ways to raise foreign currency and leasing Hambantota port to a Chinese investor, which was not generating sufficient return on investment (Moramudall 2019; Jones & Hameiri 2020). This may suggest that Sri Lanka was not in any way coerced to surrender its port to China. Bräutigam (2020) conducted a study and found no evidence of asset seizures in Africa, or indeed, anywhere among Chinese borrowers in debt difficulties.

It is for this reason that Park and Benabdallah (2021) argued that the U.S. strategy to "counter" China in Africa (and elsewhere) has resulted in generalizations about China– Africa relations that depict Chinese officials and companies as predators and Africans as their hapless victims. However, certain African governments seem to be aware of China's control. In 2018, the South African parliament called for a disclosure of a Chinese loan to Eskom, a power utility and to Transnet, a transport utility. President Cyril Ramaphosa reassured members of Parliament that Eskom would not be taken over if it defaulted on its \$2.5bn (R33.4bn at the time) loan from the Chinese Development Bank (Phakathi 2018).

Decrease in Nigerian Industries Caused by China policy

One of the detrimental effects of Chinese imports on Nigerian businesses, with textiles being the most prominent casualty. As of 2015, an estimated 28,000 Nigerians lost their jobs due to Chinese imports in Kano, which is regarded one of the biggest textiles cities in northern Nigeria (Adigbuo, 2021). Nigeria has also maintained a sizable market for Chinese commodities, which has benefited China's economy rather than Nigeria's, jeopardizing the latter's economic security. While new jobs are being created across Africa as a result of various Chinese factories, one should not be deceived as to who they are intended for: about a million Chinese people have arrived to Africa in the previous decade, and they now occupy the lion's share of the newly created positions.

Furthermore, the surge of low-cost Chinese imports has proven to be an impossible opponent for local small firms, who were already struggling without the danger. As a result, African Globe experts estimate that the African economy has suffered a loss of about \$1 billion. According to specialists from the African Globe, the increased Chinese penetration has resulted in the loss of approximately 75 000 jobs in the African economy (Umejei, 2022).

CONCLUSION

The research was focused on Nigeria China Relations and Trade development in Nigeria 2015-2022. The researcher concluded that China's socio-economic development relations with Nigeria are motivated by China's National interest and for economic gain. China sees Nigeria capable of meeting its needs for her economic and political interest to improve the welfare of her (people) citizens.

Chinese firms now dominated other sections of Nigerian economy, including agriculture, manufacturing, construction, information and communication technology, thereby destroying local industries. The study concluded that there is an equal relationship between Nigerian and China, resulting to trade imbalance and dependency on Nigeria side.

Again, the study concluded that China relations with Nigeria have revamped and financed Nigeria Agricultural sector, transportation and bilateral trade and food production.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Amongst the recommendations is that the researcher recommended that Nigeria should improve the effectiveness of its local technician training and attempt to retain them. This will determine the project's success and lay the groundwork for Nigeria's future industrialization and all loans from China should be properly channeled to projects that improve the welfare of citizens; efforts should be made to ensure accountability in the use of all loans received so that future generations are not harmed. The Nigerians' mentality that China's current trade relation is a favourable one needs to be changed. Rather, Nigeria must seek to accept only trade partnerships that would benefit the country rather than the one that will continue to limit the country. Issues of political instability, insecurity, dilapidated infrastructure, capacity building through functional education and economic diversification among others must be addressed by Nigeria against over dependence on the West and China for socio-economic development in Nigeria and that Nigerian Government should depend less on the import of goods from China since it affects economic growth in terms of real domestic product. They should start to produce their goods and consume them.

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